

HISTORY OF COTTON GROWING AND ARTIFICIAL IRRIGATION IN THE FERGANA VALLEY

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Abstract.

The importance of water in the cultivation of cotton and other agricultural products is incomparable. Therefore, special attention is paid to artificial irrigation in the Turkestan region, which has become a national affair. The rules for the use of water are reflected in the laws of Sharia as follows: The waters of rivers and lakes are considered a blessing and blessing given to people by Allah Almighty, and everyone has the right to use them equally. With the exception of ponds and wells built by private individuals, people are allowed to drink the water from them, water their livestock, and use it for their daily needs.

Keywords: Waterworks, Fergana, American variety, Namangan, Margilan, Chaykovsky, desyatina, Russia, Kokand, cotton, wheat, rice and sorghum, engineer N. Zhilin, Ulugnor stream, Kampir Ravot, Shahrihonsoy, Andijansoy.

Introduction. Everyone using water is obliged to participate in the repair and maintenance of artificial irrigation networks. Water use is carried out on a self-governing basis, and the repair of ditches and the distribution of water are entrusted to the "kokbashi" and mirobs elected by the people. They are paid in grain and other agricultural products. Mills are allowed to operate on the condition that they do not damage water structures. Rice, which requires a lot of water, can be planted with the consent of the population. In the event that water channels are laid through farm lands, a fee is paid for this.

Water has been used for centuries based on these procedures. The good thing is that arbitrariness and chaos in the use of water are eliminated. In any case, there were quarrels during times of water shortage.

Research methods and materials. By the year of registration, American cotton had taken a significant place in the agriculture of the Fergana region, with a sown area of 155,682 dessiatinas, and local cotton - 14,846 dessiatinas.

The cotton yield of the American variety was 7,996,015 poods and local cotton was 425,517 poods.

According to the figures on the cotton area and yield in the Fergana region in 1898, 38-60 poods of American cotton were harvested from one dessiatina of land, while 40-45 poods of local cotton were harvested. Even in Namangan, 62 poods of cotton were harvested from one dessiatina of land.

Cotton growing in the region was especially flourishing in Margilan uyezd, with the American variety occupying 30,000 dessiatinas of land, and the local variety occupying 2,000 dessiatinas of land. Local cotton was grown mostly in Kokand Uyezd, with a cultivated area of 7,436 dessiatines. However, despite the large quantity of this cotton, its quality and price were lower.

In 1899, the cotton area increased by 40 percent. Referring to this, the military governor of the Fergana region, Tchaikovsky, wrote in his report to the Emperor: "Now it can be said with

absolute certainty that the cultivation and development of cotton, which is extremely necessary for Russian industry, will continue to grow." He also stated that in 1899, cotton brought 20 million soums to trading firms and the population.

Tchaikovsky recommends increasing the income from cotton by 3 soums 83 kopecks per decimeter to 9-12 soums, thereby benefiting the state treasury. He indicated that, while maintaining the preferential tax on cotton, it would be necessary to collect an additional tax on it when it was sold or removed from the factory. This would bring 100 thousand soums to the state treasury.

In 1895, measures were taken to expand the Uchkurgan aqueduct in the Fergana region, and work began at the expense of the ministries of agriculture and property. However, due to the construction of the railway and the increase in wages for labor, the work almost stopped. In addition, the Russian administration drew up a project to develop 16,250 desyatina of land by diverting water from the Karadarya River in order to develop irrigation networks. However, due to insufficient funds from the government, the work was not fully implemented.

Nevertheless, the regional administration continued to ask the government about the need to develop artificial irrigation. "The climatic conditions and soil of the Fergana region," wrote the military governor Tchaikovsky, "are well suited to the requirements of cotton growing, the most valuable raw material for the textile industry. After all, agricultural crops here cannot be imagined without artificial irrigation. "Therefore, the expansion of water networks and the construction of new canals are the first task. If this is done, it will be possible to supply industry with raw materials and increase the number of Russian settlements."

Tchaikovsky also noted that the development of new lands required large expenses, but they would soon be repaid due to the fertility of the land.

It is evident that he also informed the government that the development of artificial irrigation would allow the development of new lands, increase the production of agricultural products, in particular, cotton, and at the same time create conditions for the resettlement of many Russians to the Fergana Valley.

The demands of the Russian administration to develop artificial irrigation were not without reason, of course, because the Fergana region, which was becoming a cotton mine for Russia, had very little irrigated land per capita.

According to statistical data, water networks are not evenly distributed across volosts and farms. For example, in Chimyon volost of Margilan uyezd, the per capita irrigated land area was 0.94 dessiatines, in Yakkatut 0.88, in Yozyavon and Kulin 0.77 dessiatines, while in other volosts, in particular, in Asaka 0.40, in Fayziobod 0.54 dessiatines. Previously, in Kokand village, Marhamat and Yaukesak-Boston the area exceeded one dessiatine. On average, in Margilan uyezd, the per capita irrigated land area was 0.74 dessiatines.

In Kokand uyezd, the volume of irrigated land per capita was not uniform, and in some volosts, including Naigut-Kipchokdal, 81 and Laylak, it was 0.64 desyatina. In the remaining volosts, the minimum was 0.32, 0.23, 0.42 and more desyatina. On average, irrigated land per capita in Kokand uyezd did not exceed 0.51 desyatina. The volume of irrigated land was especially small in Andijan uyezd. Here, only Naukent and Kosty included 1.28 desyatina, while in other areas it was 0.24, 0.43, 0.58, 0.59, in Kokand village 0.88 and in Maygir 0.90 desyatina. Overall, the average amount of irrigated land per capita in Andijan Uyezd was 0.65 dessiatines.

Results and discussion. By the end of the 19th century, the place of cotton in the national economy had risen to a high level. According to the regional statistics department, the Fergana Valley, with a population of one million six hundred and twenty thousand, had acquired a

significant position. Because cotton, rare fruits, and grapes are grown in accordance with the climatic conditions of this region. Cotton was especially important, bringing in an annual income of 25 million to 40 million soums. In 1900, five million pounds of cotton fiber were obtained, which provided one third of the needs of Russian industry.

According to the data showing the ratio of cotton to other crops in each volost of the region (Table 13), it is planted most in the Balikchi volost (10,390 desyatina), Norin (8,790 desyatina), and Kokand village (6,970 desyatina). Similarly, 4,000 desyatina were grown in the Ziyovuddin volost, 3,975 in Rishton, 6,980 in Shahrikhan volost, and 4,564 desyatina in Yozyavon. Andijan and Kokand uyezds were in the forefront by region.

In 1901, when cotton occupied a significant place even compared to wheat, rice, and sorghum, cotton was in the forefront among other crops:

American cotton variety....	191573
Local cotton.....	15562
Winter wheat.....	88048
Spring wheat.....	80371
Rice.....	60290
Sorghum.....	59797
Alfalfa.....	39565
Corn.....	38977
Millet.....	12120 desyatina.

The continuous planting of cotton in the same area has led to a risk of damage to cotton production. Therefore, representatives of the administration have called for the development of livestock farming and increased manure. At the same time, attention has been paid to crop rotation.

D.I. Vayykov, N. Zhilin, N. Petrov, N. Korolkov, K. Sinyavsky, G. Riesenkampf and other specialists made a great contribution to the exploration and development of projects for artificial irrigation in the Fergana Valley. Since their activities are described in S. Jalilov's book, there is no need to cover them in detail, of course. In addition, the projects and proposals prepared by them remained only on paper. S. Jalilov, who specially studied this issue, wrote: "Thus, the disagreements between tsarism and Russian capitalists on the organization of the development of new lands, the indifference of the Tsarist government to private initiative, as well as the censorship and bureaucratic mood in the Tsarist administrative departments did not allow the implementation of plans for the construction of large irrigation facilities in the Fergana Valley and the development of large areas of wasteland."

Nevertheless, it is not without benefit to consider some proposals and projects. In this regard, the opinions of Academician A. Middendorf, who in 1878 got acquainted with the state of irrigation in the Fergana Valley, are noteworthy. He proposed, first of all, to complete the work that was left unfinished during the khanate period and rely on the thousand-year experience of the indigenous population. In his opinion, it was necessary to drain the Naryn and Karadarya rivers, expand the Ulug-Nor canal, and draw up an artificial irrigation map. He proposed to build engineering structures on all large and small canals to distribute water. He indicated that the regulation and control of artificial irrigation work is the first task. "Since," he wrote, "our state, by decree, has declared all the waters of Turkestan its property, since it is necessary to use these waters for the production of food, since it is impossible to entrust irrigation facilities to companies and associations, and since it is very profitable to irrigate the land for farming with them, then it becomes an urgent duty to get down to work with speed and enthusiasm."

Engineer N. Zhilin attached special importance to the provision of water to the Ulugnor arik. He set the following tasks:

1. Reconstruction of the Ulugnor dam in Teshiktash and repair of the Tungiotar dam.
2. To connect the Bobogozi arik north of Andijan to the Ulugnor in order to provide it with regular water, and to establish control over rice planting.

On this basis, some work is being carried out. For example, a certain part of the Ulugnor arik is being cleaned, its banks are being raised with a dam, and the risk of flooding is being prevented. A dam is being built on the Bobogozi arik and diverted to Ulugnor. The Tungiotar and Teshiktash dams are also being rebuilt. However, these works only regulated artificial irrigation to a certain extent, and only a small amount of money (1,100 soums) was spent on them. Due to the lack of sufficient funds from the administration, N. Zhilin's project to improve the Ulugnor arik to the required level was abandoned. Representatives of the administration restored the Musulmonkul arik, which had become quite dilapidated, albeit to a certain extent, with the help of the people, and as a result, the water supply to the villages improved somewhat. Also, in Kampir Ravat, hashars were organized to provide regular water to the Shahrikhonsoy and Andijansoy, the largest in the valley. However, not all work aimed at developing artificial irrigation was completed. In addition, floods undermined the work done.

At the beginning of the 20th century, efforts to regulate and develop artificial irrigation did not stop, but representatives of the central government did not pay sufficient attention to this work. At that time, a project was drawn up to radically improve the Ulugnor arik, and a request was made to Petersburg for funding. However, a negative response was received there. After that, business in the region was mainly limited to the sphere of influence of the Russian administration in the region. On the instructions of the governor-general of the region, the digging of the Balikchi arik, as a continuation of the Ulugnor arik, began and this work was completed. Artificial irrigation was also significantly regulated in Shahrikhonsay, and the cultivated area reached 60 thousand dessiatina.

Conclusion. In this way, artificial irrigation networks have been effective, largely through the power of the people. In 1917, the area of irrigated land in the country was distributed by watershed as follows:

-245,000 in the Syrdarya basin, 225,000 in Chirchik, Keles, Kuru-Keles, Akhangaron, 140,000 in Talas, Avliyoata district, 141,000 on the Chu River, 70,000 on Issyk-Kul, 297,000 on Lake Balkhash, 106,000 on the Sanzor stream, 393,000 on Zarafshon and Kattakurgan, 172,000 on the Murghab and Tejen streams, 64,000 on the Amu Darya, a total of 2,853,000 desyatina.

Thus, as a result of the large amount of water taken from the Syrdarya, Zarafshan and Chirchik rivers, the area of cultivated land in the country was considered much higher than in other places. As noted in the previous pages, the entire burden of repairing and cleaning artificial irrigation fell entirely on the shoulders of the population. According to sources, in addition to ordinary taxes, the people paid three types of taxes, which included expenses for combating locusts, repairing roads and bridges, and artificial irrigation. Among them, the "Irrigation duties" (Artificial irrigation tax) was especially heavy.

The Russian government tried to develop cotton cultivation by expanding and repairing artificial irrigation networks left over from the khanate period to a certain extent.

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